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Experimental Evaluation of a Laboratory-Scale Drum Type Testing Machine for Analysis of Tire Performance

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ABSTRACT

The Tire of vehicle is a crucial part that contributes to the overall economy of the vehicle. The tire has a large impact on fuel saving capability. It carries the overall load of the vehicle, including the passengers and their goods. Proper pressure and proper gas are required to have maximum efficiency of the tire which results in the maximum fuel economy. Thermal stability, Rolling resistance, and the thermal variation of the tire are the parameters which are responsible for the performance of the vehicle. This paper presents the experimental evaluation for the analysis of a 145 / 80 R12 74T tire, using the laboratory scale drum type testing machine. The tire testing was done at the various conditions of 30 to 34 psi. The tire performance was tested at uniform tire pressure and at various load conditions like 25 %, 50%, 75% of the tires highest recommended load and at variable speed. The tire was tested by inflating it with air and nitrogen. The results show that as the load and speed gets increased the rolling resistance and the temperature of the tire also gets increased. It was observed that, by using the nitrogen gas, the rolling resistance and the temperature of the tire was significantly reduced.

Keywords: Drum-type testing, rolling resistance, nitrogen, thermal analysis, tire performance

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of passenger car tires is to connect the vehicle to the road surface. In a typical mid-size car, the total rubber area touching the road from all four tires is smaller than a standard $8\frac{1}{2} \times 11$ -inch sheet of paper. Each tire touches the road over an area roughly the size of a person's hand. When the vehicle carries weight, the tires compress until the pressure inside the tire balances the pressure at the contact area with the road.[1] The main forces that control a vehicle's performance are generated by the surface contact between the road and tire. Therefore, it is crucial to clearly understand how tires behave, especially the forces and moments they produce under different operating conditions.[2] When a passenger vehicle is running, different types of losses reduce its fuel efficiency. These include losses from the engine, drivetrain, air resistance, and rolling resistance. Engine, drivetrain, and aerodynamic losses are built into the vehicle because of its many mechanical components. Rolling resistance, however, comes from the tires, which are the only parts that directly touch the road.[8]

Rolling resistance plays an important role in vehicle movement and directly affects fuel consumption. Many studies have examined how factors such as load, tire pressure, and speed influence rolling resistance, with the aim of improving fuel efficiency. Recent research also suggests that filling tires with nitrogen helps maintain stable pressure and slows down rubber degradation.[3] Therefore the study focuses on the experimental evaluation for the analysis of a 145 / 80 R12 74T tire, using the laboratory scale drum type testing machine. The tire testing was done at the various conditions of 30 to 34 psi. The evaluation of tire performance was tested at standard inflation pressure and at various load like 25 %, 50%, 75% of the

highest recommended load of tire and also at variable speed. The tire was tested by inflating it with the nitrogen gas and Air. The results show that as the load and speed get increased rolling resistance and the temperature of the tire also gets increased. It was observed that, by using the nitrogen gas, the rolling resistance and the temperature of the tire was significantly reduced.

The aim of this study is to compare the tires filled with nitrogen and those filled with air so as to improve vehicle safety and overall performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

When a tire is maintained at the correct pressure, it ensures safer driving, better grip on the road, stable handling, longer service life, and improved fuel efficiency. Low tire pressure is a common and serious issue. When the pressure drops, rolling resistance increases, which leads to higher fuel consumption. An under-inflated tire also bends more while rotating, causing uneven tread wear and increased heat generation.[4] The initial purity of nitrogen inside a tire can vary depending on the tire's maximum inflation pressure, the quality of nitrogen used, and the filling method followed at the service station. When a tire is first filled with nitrogen and later topped up with air, the amount of oxygen entering the tire over its lifetime is still reduced. Most of this advantage is seen during the early period of the tire's service life.[5] Tire rolling resistance (RR) is one of the main energy sinks for electric passenger vehicles, having a large impact on driving range and lifecycle fuel consumption. Accurate predictions of range and consumption in non-ideal conditions require the ability to model tire RR in a broad range of temperatures and for any given drive cycle [6,9]

Rolling Resistance

Studying tire inflation pressure is important because it directly affects a vehicle's fuel consumption. Rolling resistance is influenced by several factors, including tire design, applied load, and vehicle speed. However, inflation pressure has a strong effect since it controls the size of the contact portion between road and tire. As the tire is the only part of the vehicle that touches the road surface, maintaining the correct pressure is essential. Proper inflation helps maintain an optimal contact patch and reduces resistance to motion. In addition, the materials used in the tire and the arrangement of the belt layers influence how forces are distributed at the tire-road contact area. These construction features play a key role in determining the overall performance of the tire.[1]

Rolling resistance has a strong effect on overall vehicle performance and fuel efficiency of a vehicle. Because of this, vehicle manufacturers focus on improving the overall economy of the vehicles they produce each year. To achieve this, tires are often designed to be lighter and to generate lower rolling resistance. This is done by using thinner sidewalls, reduced tread depth, and specially developed tread compounds and constructions that are intended to minimize energy loss.[10]

Although tire design and material selection do influence rolling resistance, operating conditions such as load (L), inflation pressure (P), and vehicle speed (V) have a much stronger effect over time. Fuel economy reflects how much resistance the vehicle must overcome while moving. These resistances include inertia, drivetrain friction, aerodynamic drag, road slope variations, and rolling resistance. Understanding the contribution of each factor is essential for improving overall efficiency. Focusing specifically on rolling

resistance, it accounts for roughly 15% of total vehicle resistance in city driving and about 25% during highway driving.[7]

IMPACT OF INFLATION PRESSURE ON TIRE BEHAVIOR

It is necessary to examine how tire inflation pressure affects vehicle fuel usage. Rolling resistance depends on several factors, including tire design, applied load, and driving speed. However, inflation pressure has a major impact because it controls the size of the area where the tire touches the road. Since the tire is the only component in direct contact with the road surface, maintaining the correct pressure is very important. Proper inflation helps keep the contact area at an optimal level and reduces resistance to motion. In addition, the type of materials used in the tire and the arrangement of the belt layers determine how forces are distributed at the tire-road contact surface. These construction details significantly affect the overall performance of the tire.[3,11]

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The drum-type testing setup has a straight forward design, and it is easier to manufacture as compared to other tire testing setups. It is also convenient to operate and conduct experiments on it. Due to these advantages, the drum-type setup is chosen for the tire evaluation. This setup is primarily used to measure various factors such as rolling resistance, tire wear and the tire temperature.

The drum diameter is determined in accordance with the SAE J1269 rolling resistance testing standard, which specifies a drum diameter of 1.2 m to ensure standardized curvature and repeatable test conditions. Mild steel is selected for drum fabrication due to its favorable mechanical properties, including sufficient yield strength, structural rigidity, machinability, and cost-effectiveness. These properties

ensure dimensional stability under repeated loading during tire testing.[12]

The test rig setup for tire analysis is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Test Rig Setup for Tire Analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The tire selected for the evaluation of tire performance is 145/80 R12 74T. In this designation, 145 mm represents the nominal section width, and the aspect ratio of 80 indicates that the sidewall height is 80 percent of the section width. The letter “R” confirms that the tire has radial ply construction, while 12 specifies the rim diameter in inches. The load index 74 corresponds to a load carrying capacity of 375 kg per tire, and the speed rating “T” permits operation up to 190 km/h under recommended conditions.

To evaluate rolling resistance and temperature characteristics, the tire is tested using a 10 kW variable-speed DC motor integrated into the test rig. The

motor drives the drum assembly, allowing the tire to rotate at controlled speeds. During experimentation, the rotational speed is adjusted between approximately 300 rpm and 690 rpm, which simulates vehicle speeds ranging from 30 km/h to 65 km/h. The test facility is designed to accommodate tires with a maximum overall diameter of 0.75 m. Vertical loading is applied through a mechanically operated loading screw mounted on the test bench, enabling controlled and repeatable load application.

The applied load values are selected based on established industry standards, namely SAE J1269, SAE J918C, and SAE J1561, to maintain consistency with recognized testing procedures.[13,14]

Table 1: Performance Analysis at 30 psi (Compressed Air).

Speed (km/h)	Load (N)	Power (W)	Rolling Resistance (N)	Tire Temp (°C)
35	920	450	46.30	44.1
	1840	1295	133.20	48.2
	2760	2410	247.90	50.8
45	920	655	53.20	45.4
	1840	1855	148.40	49.3
	2760	3380	270.40	52.1
55	920	950	62.18	46.6

	1840	2580	168.87	50.9
	2760	4625	302.73	54.2
65	920	1195	66.18	47.9
	1840	3220	178.34	52.6
	2760	5750	318.46	56.4
75	920	1550	74.40	49.5
	1840	4250	204.00	54.8
	2760	7600	364.80	59.1

This Table 1 represents the under-inflated condition, showing the highest relative values for rolling resistance and thermal buildup across all loads.

Table 2: Performance Analysis at 32 psi (Standard Inflation).

Speed (km/h)	Load (N)	Power (W) - Air	RR - Air (N)	Temp - Air (°C)	Power (W) - Nitrogen	RR - Nitrogen (N)	Temp - Nitrogen (°C)
35	920	345	35.5	42.2	315	32.4	41.1
	1840	1072	110.3	46	998	102.6	43.8
	2760	2298	236.4	48.8	2137	219.8	46.4
45	920	508	40.6	43	473	37.8	42
	1840	1433	114.6	47	1378	110.2	45.2
	2760	3094	247.5	50.1	2939	235.1	48.3
55	920	701	45.9	44.1	660	43.2	42.9
	1840	1815	118.8	48	1748	114.4	46.3
	2760	3957	259	51.5	3798	248.6	49.7
65	920	950	52.6	45.5	899	49.8	44.7
	1840	2441	135.2	50.1	2353	130.3	47.7
	2760	4920	272.5	52.8	4723	261.6	50.8
75	920	1246	59.8	47.2	1177	56.5	45.9
	1840	3238	155.4	52.3	3108	149.2	49.6
	2760	6567	315.2	55.4	6304	302.6	52.1

This data [Table 2] compares the performance of Compressed Air versus Dry Nitrogen at the standard recommended pressure.

Table 3: Performance Analysis at 34 psi (Over-inflation).

Speed (km/h)	Load (N)	Power (W)	Rolling Resistance (N)	Tire Temp (°C)
35	920	335.5	34.5	40.9
	1840	1045	107.5	45.1
	2760	1590.2	163.56	47.1
45	920	473.6	37.89	42.1
	1840	1378	110.24	45.8
	2760	2139.5	171.16	48
55	920	660	43.2	43.3
	1840	1748.5	114.44	46.9
	2760	2743	179.54	49.2
65	920	899.6	49.82	44.2
	1840	2353.6	130.35	48.1

	2760	3481	192.79	50.2
75	920	1177	56.5	45.3
	1840	3108.5	149.21	49.8
	2760	4752	228.1	51.9

This Table 3 represents the over-inflated condition, which typically results in the lowest power consumption and temperature rise.

Key Summary of Results

- Pressure and Rolling Resistance: Increasing inflation pressure significantly reduces rolling resistance across all loads; for example, at a 2760 N load and 65 km/h, the resistance dropped from 318.46 N at 30 psi to 192.79 N at 34 psi.
- Thermal Efficiency and Fluid Type: Higher pressures and the use of Nitrogen result in cooler operating temperatures, with Nitrogen-inflated tires

- at 32 psi running 2.0°C cooler (49.2°C) than air-inflated tires (51.2°C) under a 1962 N load.
- Power Demand and Efficiency: Power demand peaks under under-inflated, high-load conditions, reaching 3515 W at 29 psi (1962 N load); however, at the 2760 N maximum load, switching from 30 psi (5750 W) to 34 psi (3481 W) results in a total energy saving of approximately 39.4%. [15,16]

Impact of Tire Pressure on Rolling Resistance

Figures 2, 3 and 4 shows the results of Impact of Tire Pressure on Rolling Resistance at various speed and load.

Fig. 2: Impact of Tire Pressure on Rolling Resistance at 920 N Load.

Fig. 3: Impact of Tire Pressure on Rolling Resistance at 1840 N Load.

Fig. 4: Impact of Tire Pressure on Rolling Resistance at 2760 N Load.

From above Figures 2 to 4, it can be seen that rolling resistance increases as the load and speed increase, whereas it decreases when the tire pressure is raised. The highest rolling resistance value, 195 N, was recorded at a load of 1962 N, while the lowest value, 29 N, was observed at a load of 804 N. These results show that

rolling resistance is lower at lower load and lower speed conditions.[17]

Impact of Tire Pressure on Tire Temperature

Figure 5, 6 and 7 shows the results of Impact of Tire Pressure on Tire Temperature at various speed and load.

Fig. 5: Impact of Tire Pressure on Tire Temperature at 920 N Load.

Fig. 6: Impact of Tire Pressure on Tire Temperature at 1840 N Load.

Fig. 7: Impact of Tire Pressure on Tire Temperature at 2760 N Load.

The influence of tire pressure on tire temperature at different speeds and loads is shown in Figures 5 to 7. The results indicate that tire temperature rises as the load and speed increase. On the other hand, increasing the inflation pressure leads to a reduction in tire temperature.[18]

Impact of Air and Nitrogen on Rolling Resistance and Tire Temperature

At a constant inflation pressure of 32 psi, the effects of load and speed on rolling resistance and tire temperature were examined for tires filled with air and nitrogen. The results obtained from this comparison are shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Fig. 8: Rolling Resistance Comparison: Compressed Air vs Nitrogen (32 PSI, Variable Loads and Speeds).

Fig. 9: Tire Temperature comparison: Compressed Air vs Nitrogen (32 PSI, Variable Loads and Speeds).

Figures 8 and 9 show that for both air-filled and nitrogen-filled tires, rolling resistance and tire temperature rise as the load and speed increase. However, at the same inflation pressure of 32 psi, the increase is smaller in the case of nitrogen compared to air.[19,20]

CONCLUSION

A drum-type tire testing rig was designed and developed to evaluate rolling resistance and tire temperature under controlled laboratory conditions in accordance with SAE J1269 standards. The experiments were conducted at speeds ranging from 35 to 75 km/h, loads of 920 N, 1840 N, and 2760 N, and inflation pressures of 30, 32, and 34 psi.

The results show that rolling resistance and tire temperature increase as load and speed increase, due to higher deformation and energy dissipation within the tire structure. Conversely, increasing the inflation pressure reduces rolling resistance and temperature, primarily because of reduced contact patch area and lower hysteresis losses.

Comparative testing between air and nitrogen inflation shows that nitrogen-filled tires exhibit slightly lower rolling resistance and operating temperature under identical conditions.

The developed drum-type setup proved effective for evaluating tire performance parameters under different working conditions.

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